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Tivadar Gaudenyi¹, Đordije Božović², Petar Stejić³, Draženko Nenadić⁴

SUPERFICIAL GEOLOGY OF LOWER KOLUBARA AND KOLUBARSKA POSAVINA

POVRŠINSKA GEOLOGIJA DONJE KOLUBARE I KOLUBARSKE POSAVINE

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Abstract: The study has aimed to evaluate the recent studies regarding the geological and geomorphological mapping of the area of Lower Kolubara and Kolubarska Posavina.

The results of field studies suggest that the left bank of Kolubara valley from the confluence of Tamnava river is mainly composed of alluvial fans from the tributaries of the Kolubara river. Previous studies this fans identified as the terraces of Kolubara.

The sedimentary provenance of the Kolubarska Posavina can be separated on two main segments. The west segment of Kolubarska Posavina mainly composed of former meanders and alluvial plain ending eastwards with the older - Zvečka (paleo)meander of Sava River belongs to the Sava River sedimentary system. The eastern segment which has been created from the former remnants of the (macro) alluvial fan of the Kolubara floodplain sediments of the Kolubara encompass the area eastwards from the older – Zvečka (paleo)meander of Sava River which considered as the sedimentary area of the Kolubara river.

Key words: Kolubara; Sava; fluvial terraces; alluvial fan; geomorphology.

Apstrakt: Studija je imala za cilj da uradi evaulaciju novijih istraživanja u vezi sa geološkim i geomorfološkim kartiranjem područja Donje Kolubare i Kolubarske Posavine.

Rezultati terenskih istraživanja ukazuju da je leva obala doline Kolubare, od ušća reke Tamnave, uglavnom sastavljena od plavinskih zastora nastalih spajanjem aluvijalnih lepeza, koje su formirali pritoke reke Kolubare. Ranija istraživanja su plavinski zastor identifikovala kao terase Kolubare.

Sedimenti Kolubarske Posavine mogu se podeliti na dve glavne provincije. Zapadni segment Kolubarske Posavine, koji je uglavnom sastavljen od bivših meandara i sedimenata aluvijalne ravni, završava prema istoku sa starim (paleomeanderom) meandrom reke Save (kod Zvečke), i

¹ Geographical Institute “Jovan Cvijić” of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts; Djure Jakšića 9; 11000 Belgrade, Serbia.

² Belgrade Waterworks and Sewerage, Deligradska 28, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia.

³ Geological Survey of Serbia; Rovinjska 14, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia.

⁴ Faculty of Mining and Geology, University of Belgrade, Kamenička 6, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia.

pripada sedimentacionom sistemu reke Save. Istočni segment, koji je nastao od bivših ostataka (makro)plavine i sedimenata inundacione ravni Kolubare, obuhvata područje istočno od starog (paleomeandra) reke Save i smatra se sedimentacionim područjem reke Kolubare.

Ključne reči: Kolubara, Sava, rečne terase, aluvijalne lepeze, geomorfologija.

INTRODUCTION

Previous geological records (FILIPOVIĆ et al, 1980; STEJIĆ, 1997) have revealed that the lower segment of the Kolubara River experiences considerable dynamism, marked by a series of transformations. Land-surface dynamics and hydrological processes in this area, including notable bank erosion, lateral channel migration, and cut-offs, are influenced by both natural factors and human activities. Being a meandering river in the lowland, the Lower Kolubara responds diversely to valley-slope deformations triggered by active tectonics, depending on the pace and extent of lateral migration and bank erosion. Mapping of active tectonic movements (MAROVIĆ et al., 2007) in the Kolubara basin illustrates widespread subsidence in the lower valley region, propelled by tectonic activity in the southern part of the Pannonian Plain. Discharge is acknowledged as the primary force sculpting the riverbed, with the Kolubara river exhibiting the highest discharge variation coefficient among Serbia's major river basins, resulting in an unequal ratio between high and low water levels (DRAGIĆEVIĆ et al., 2016). The river's unfavorable water regime leads to excessive runoff, characterized by sudden, intense, and short-lived floods. Consequently, hydrological characteristics and extreme events are evaluated alongside bank erosion. Human interventions in the hydrological network, particularly since 1959 when significant regulatory measures were enacted, have had profound repercussions. These interventions, including redirecting the Kolubara channel into the Peštan tributary, have exacerbated lateral channel migration, resulting in significant socio-economic and environmental consequences such as loss of arable land, changes in land use, flood risks, and economic losses due to diminished agricultural productivity (DRAGIĆEVIĆ et al., 2016).

The Kolubarska Posavina in the last few decades were in the focus of studies in geosciences – mainly related to the torrents, bank erosion and sediment discharge (e.g. ROKSANDIĆ et al., 2011, PETROVIĆ et al., 2015, DRAGIĆEVIĆ et al., 2007, 2012, 2016, 2017). The geological mapping (FILIPOVIĆ et al, 1980; STEJIĆ, 1997) shows several uncertainties related to right bank of the Sava River along the widen area of Obrenovac town. It is mainly related of the landforms in the area of the Kolubarska Posavina to distinguish the terraces and the remnants of the alluvial fans. Moreover, the research history of the Kolubara Basin during the last several decades shows some uncertainties (e.g. in the case of landforms on the relation: alluvial fan or terrace), related to the relief and superficial geology of the area (e.g. slope sediments or terrace sediments). The importance of the investigations of the Posavska Kolubara related to the vulnerability to the floods of Obrenovac town, further possibilities to use the groundwaters for water supply in the system of the Belgrade aquifer and the relief of the Kolubara valley and possibility for the activation of landslides.

This study will not repeat the focus on torrents and climate interactions it has been already done in some previous studies (e.g. BURIĆ et al., 2012; DRAGIĆEVIĆ et al., 2007, 2013, 2016; PETROVIĆ et al., 2014, 2015). In our investigations the superficial deposits of the Lower Kolubara and Kolubarska Posavina are in the focus which will serve the basic information for other studies such as urban planing etc.

Aims

Objectives of this study focused on the investigations of the Quaternary geology and geomorphology in the Lower Kolubara and Kolubarska Posavina based on the sedimentological record and relief characteristics. The final product planned to be the geological sketch with identification of sedimentary provenance in the area of Posavska Kolubara regarding of Sava and/or Kolubara sedimentary domain(s) and if needed some corrections of existing geomorphological/ geological data.

The importance of this study of superficial deposits should give perception and a crucial basis of analysis for the investigations of floods vulnerability, groundwater potential and land surface dynamics. The geological mapping shows several uncertainties related to the right bank of the Sava River along the widen area of Obrenovac town. Research of the Lower Kolubara and Posavska Kolubara during the last several decades shows some uncertainty, related to the relief and geology of the Kolubara Basin.

Study area

The Kolubara River is the right tributary of the Sava River, within the western region of Serbia. Its catchment is located in the region of Šumadija in Central Serbia. According to KOSTADINOV et al. (2017) the Kolubara Basin 3,641 km² covers about 4.2% of Serbian territory. The apex of a catchment's drainage area ascends 1,346 m asl (located in the area of Povlen Mt. peak), while the lowest 76 m altitude (located in the area of Kolubara River confluence in the Sava River). The Kolubara River is 86.4 km long, covering 3,641 km² of the catchment (denominated as Kolubara Basin), thus according to DRAGIĆEVIĆ et al., (2012) it belongs to medium-sized river basins in Serbia.

The importance of Kolubara Basin is high, because it is defined as a densely populated area with its approx. 317,000 inhabitants, it means about 87 persons per km² (KOSTADINOV et al., 2017).

The Kolubara River flows through diverse terrains. The Kolubara Basin is made up of Mesozoic and Cenozoic igneous- and sedimentary rocks, as well as metamorphic rocks of Palaeozoic age (DRAGIĆEVIĆ et al., 2017).

After Jovanović, (1956) the Kolubara Basin can be divided into:

- the Upper Kolubara Basin or Upper Kolubara (*Gornjokolubarski basen*) in the south;
- the Lower Kolubara Basin or Lower Kolubara (*Donjokolubarski basen*) in the north.

The Lower Kolubara located in the lowland area where the widen area of Kolubarska Posavina (which is in the focus of this study) positioned. The lowland area

of Lower Kolubara considered as an integral part of the Pannonian Plain (Ćalić et al., 2012a, 2012b; Gaudenyi & Mihajlović, 2022a) and the Alföld (Gaudenyi & Mihajlović, 2022b) in wider context belongs to the Carpathian Basin (Gaudenyi & Mihajlović, 2022c).

KOSTADINOV et al., (2017) analyzed the hypsometric features of the Kolubara Basin area and stated the following:

- The lowlands and the area of hilly region were identified of 41.82% (1521.38 km²) of its total Kolubara Basin area which lies below 200 m asl.

- The low mountains region identified at elevations in between 200 m asl and 500 m asl. The low mountains area encompasses its 47.73% (1736.78 km²) of the Kolubara Basin. Consequently, a significant portion of 89.55% (3258.16 km²) of the Kolubara Basin located up to 500 m asl.

- The mountains region with 9.98% (362.9 km²) of the Kolubara Basin has heights in the range of 500 and 1000 m asl.

- The high mountains region was a mere 0.48% (17.39 km²) of the Kolubara Basin above 1000 m.

According to the above mentioned data, it is calculated that the mean elevation at the Kolubara Basin amounts 76.4 m asl. The main three groups of elevations (lowland and hills, low mountains, and mountains) encompass 99.53% of the Kolubara Basin (KOSTADINOV et al., 2017).

In terms of slope angles, areas with slope angles up to 10° cover 72.7% of the catchment area, areas with slope angles from 10° to 20° comprise 25%, and areas with slope angles over 20° make up 2.6% of the catchment area. The mean slope angle of the Kolubara catchment is 6.1° (KOSTADINOV et al., 2017).

Analysis of the yearly precipitation records (spanning from 1959 to 2010 within the Kolubara River catchment (DRAGIĆEVIĆ, 2007; PETROVIĆ et al., 2014, 2015) suggests a continental-pluviometric regime. This regime is characterized by its highest rainfall typically observed at the start of summer and lowest precipitation levels during winter. Over the specified time frame, the average annual rainfall in the Kolubara River catchment amounted to 809 mm (DRAGIĆEVIĆ et al., 2016). The detailed climate, and climate-flood relations of the Kolubara has been already published in BURIC et al., (2012) and DRAGIĆEVIĆ et al., (2007).

According to PETROVIĆ et al. (2015) the Kolubara River at the utmost limits, its maximum discharge measured for Draževac profile to the period 1959–2016 was recorded on May 15th 2014 (Q_{max}=1260 m³/s), while absolute minimum discharge on August 25th 2000. (Q_{min}=0.60 m³/s) (DRAGIĆEVIĆ et al., 2016). The ratio between the absolute maximum and absolute minimum discharge is approximately 1200 m³/s. May marks the peak of flood occurrences (33 or 27.3%) occasionally it could be June (22 or 18.2%) also during the summer months, while the second peak is associated with March (18 or 14.9%) in the colder months. In the same study of PETROVIĆ et al. (2015) have indicated that the Kolubara Basin possesses all the necessary conditions for frequent and large-scale flash floods, it initiated with the wet air masses from the northwest and topography of study area resulted with a watershed runoff coefficient by shape factor of 0.79 (which is quite rare). Moreover, significant deforestation and

torrential flow patterns of numerous tributaries, geological and soil characteristics in the lower river catchment (due to limited retention capacity), high sediment accumulation in the riverbed, as well as anthropogenic impacts and urbanization resulted with torrents. The Kolubara Basin ranks 4th in Serbia according to the recorded torrential floods (PETROVIĆ et al., 2015). These specific types of floods pose various challenges as they result in numerous repercussions. The first major recorded torrential flood in the Kolubara Basin dates back to the floods on the Ljubostinja-, Gradac-, Krivošija Rivers, and Upper Kolubara on 18 April 1929 (PETROVIĆ et al., 2015). In addition, common floods are often registered on the Tamnava River and its tributaries Ub- and Gračanica Rivers. The most severe floods in recent years occurred in 1999, 2006, 2009 and 2014. In 1999 the flood covers 6000 ha, in 2006 almost 5600 ha was flooded, in 2009 - 3000 ha flooded (STEFANOVIĆ et al., 2015). Moreover, the last recorded and the biggest floods in the Kolubara catchment was in 2014, with the torrents of Kolubara river as well as its tributaries Tamnava-, Jablanica-, Obnica-, Gradac-, Ribnica-, Ljig-, Peštan-, Ub Rivers (PROHASKA & ZLATANOVIĆ, 2016). The total flooded area in Serbia was about 20.000 km² some 32,000 people were evacuated from their homes, out of which 25,000 were from the town of Obrenovac (STEFANOVIĆ et al., 2015).

The Kolubara River has been categorized as a natural phenomenon due to the fact that in the early 2000s, there was a flood wave larger than the typical once-in-fifty-years occurrence almost biannual (DRAGIČEVIĆ et al., 2007, 2016). Based on KOSTADINOV et al., (2017) the soil data analysis derived from CORINE land cover 2012 (hereinafter: CLC) indicates that within Serbia, 20 CLC types identified as present in the Kolubara Basin. It is evident that the most prevalent type is CLC 243 (cultivated land with significant natural vegetation), covering 29.56% of the area, continued with the 242 types (complex cultivation patterns) at 28.4%, and 311 types (deciduous species) at 23.49% of the river catchment area. Cultivated land (CLC 211 type) accounts for slightly over 10% of the total area, due to its geomorphological and hydrological features. Kolubara Basin belongs to the area that is prone to a higher frequency occurrence of natural hazards in a form of floods and bank erosion.

The vertical relief dissection, terrain slopes, and extreme water discharges indicate the vulnerability of the area to flash floods. These flash floods are triggered by intense precipitation or sudden snow melt, characterized by rapidly forming torrential waves. These waves are highly concentrated with debris, short-lived, and result in significant damage. In contrast to larger rivers, where high water levels persist for an extended period, allowing for timely flood response and management, flash floods present a different challenge. Due to their rapid formation, there is limited time for preventive measures, leading to a swift transition from regular flood control to emergency response. Therefore, monitoring plays a crucial role in managing flash floods. Instances of sudden flash floods are closely linked to torrential floods characterized by specific hydrological and sedimentary regimes. The sediment output within the watershed involves the relocation of materials from catchments to streams and their subsequent transport through the hydrographic network (KOSTADINOV et al., 2017).

Torrential floods are characterized by a small amount of water throughout the year, but they experience significant discharges after heavy rainfall. This results in a

two-phased stream, where in addition to the liquid phase of water, there is a substantial amount of debris being transported. This combination poses a higher risk of river bed overflow.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Advancements in computerized infrastructure, enhanced computing power, and increased data storage capabilities have led to the emergence of cloud-based computing platforms. These platforms offer on-demand access to high-performance computing facilities without the need to own and maintain physical hardware (SUDMANN et al., 2020).

This may possibly revolutionize farther detecting applications in geomorphology. The stages can bolster very large information capacity, making a difference to resolve information escalated issues related with the huge volumes of Earth observation information (YANG et al., 2020). In case of such a stage is Google Earth Engine (GEE), a cloud-based computing stage, open through a web-based interface, for planetary-scale geospatial examination (GORELICK et al., 2017). GEE holds an information catalog of freely accessible unreservedly available remotely detected imagery (within Landsat and Sentinel database), environmental and other geospatial information sets. The cloud-based computing stage adjusts with the concept of virtualization, liberating clients from asset administration and concerns around their physical usage (LEE et al., 2011), meaning that researchers can bring their possess calculations to the datasets (WULDER & COOPS, 2014).

Virtualization permits researchers to connected with Earth observation information without contributing in computing and information administration foundation (GIULIANI et al., 2020), expelling calculated and know-how limitations from resource-poor researchers (MUTANGA & KUMAR, 2019).

“A key distinction is made here between Google Earth, a virtual globe for viewing digital imagery of the Earth's surface (TOOTH, 2013) and GEE, a planetary-scale platform for analyzing geospatial information (GOOGLE, 2020).” (BOOTHROYD et al., 2021). GEE isn't the as it were cloud-based computing stage accessible, Earth on Amazon Web Services moreover gives on-demand cloud-based computing assets, in spite of the fact that the registry of Earth perception and geospatial information is as of now (in 2020) obscure than that of GEE (BOOTHYORD et al., 2021).

A modern mapping and stock of both outcrop and subsurface information have been carried out to decode the Quaternary evolution and get it the expansion, genesis and relationship of these Quaternary units and the dissemination of clastics from diverse source regions. The later carrying out of broad respectful works and the expanding open-pit (exposures) extraction of alluvial materials have empowered a careful and detailed survey of Quaternary units of the Sava river valley and the Kolubara river valley. Since of the regularly destitute, limited and scattered outcrop conditions of these units, point by point mapping has been carried out at following the topographical map at 1:25,000 scale. The information which was from aforementioned paper maps were the pivot point to consultation Google Earth tool. It was very useful to avoid the high accumulation a debris material and to find a prospective point for

open exposure, where the soil / sediment sampling will be possible. It continues with the field survey. The field survey was started by cleaning the exposure surface and describing the lithological column or with a simple fixed-handle auger (manufacturer Royal Eijkelkamp) for extracting sediment samples for sedimentological analysis. The soil / sediment analysis done in field by the using grain size card (GEO Supplies Ltd) and binoculars due the identifying the clasts shape – angularity, stratification and grain size distribution. Field work and analyses were following the protocol and recommendations of JONES et al., (1999). Topographical segments have been made on the premise of the advanced landscape demonstrate, which permits perception of critical geomorphological characteristics that seem not be dissected once in the past. Additionally, the stock of reports and explanatory sheets from the Geological Survey of Serbia overviews is presently accessible and has made strides subsurface information and empowered setting up a relationship with the outcropping units.

Summarizing, the investigations were based on the reference literature and the geological map by STEJIĆ (1997). The area was expanded with its eastern part from the data of the Obrenovac sheet of Basic Geological Map of Yugoslavia (FILIPOVIĆ et al., 1980). It continues with the field survey and remote sensing based on Google Earth tool help us to make a final decision to identify the fluvial sedimentary system which predominates in the area of Lower Kolubara and Kolubarska Posavina.

RESULTS

Summarizing the results a general appearance of Quaternary deposits in the Kolubarska Posavina and their relationship to the peripheral Neogene formations suggest that this is a tectonically affected area where under the dominant influence of fluvial processes, technogenic sediments have been deposited (made some the path changes of the tributaries of the Kolubara river), as well as proluvial, deluvial, and eolian agents. Among the distinguished lithostratigraphic units (FILIPOVIĆ et al., 1980; STEJIĆ, 1997), based on lithological, sedimentological, and petrological characteristics identified during the field survey, those belonging to the Sava River sedimentary area can be clearly differentiated from deposits formed in the Kolubara (and Tamnava) Valley, the main tributary, and rivers that flow parallel to it. Essentially the analysis at field survey and evaluation of map data, the main difference lies in the fact that the material deposited in the influence zone of the Sava River is coarser and more varied in composition compared to the fine-grained material of very uniform petrological composition in the Lower Kolubara. This natural difference arises due to different source areas of material that form Quaternary formations in the studied areas. The strong flow of the Sava carries material resulting from the erosion of both the main stream and tributaries that collects in the sedimentary record earlier than in the Kolubarska Posavina. On the other hand, Kolubara and other right tributaries of the Sava River flow mainly through Neogene or older Quaternary terrains, carrying and depositing predominantly fine-grained material of uniform composition.

According to Shantser's model (SHANTSER, 1951) of the multi-phase nature of river valleys, it can be concluded that the Sava River is in a constructive dynamic phase during the Quaternary in the investigated area. It representing a meandering type of

river with frequent channel shifts, strong floods, numerous terraces, and a very wide alluvial plain (Fig 1). During the older Quaternary (relative time context), cyclic-fluvial sediments of significant thickness were deposited, representing the main collector of groundwater suitable for water supply. Tamnava River, along with other rivers south of the Sava, is in a perstrative dynamic phase during the Quaternary, forming monocyclic river terraces of complex floodplain type. The valleys of these rivers, continue upstream, and have been outside the investigated area, which are in the transitive dynamic phase, or in the incision process.

Fig. 1. The cyclic fluvial sedimentation model of Shantser (1951) recognized in the case of Sava River valley. Legend: 1. riverbed alluvium; 2. oxbow alluvium; 3. floodplain alluvium; 4. secondary basin sediments; H - floodplain water level; h - average water table level; h₁ h₂ – average water table level in oxbow lakes and secondary basins; M – normal alluvium thickness; M_s – total alluvium thickness.

The genesis of Quaternary deposits in the Lower Kolubara and Kolubarska Posavina is influenced by climatic changes and the neotectonic subsidence. During the Early- and Middle Pleistocene, the tectonic trough of the Sava River experienced continuous subsidence, resulting in the deposition river sediments increased thickness their thickness with tens of meters. These sediments consist mainly of gravel and sand in older sections and sands, gravel, and organogenic-bar sediments in younger parts. The increased thickness of these deposits is interpreted as tectonic subsidence, while the large quantity and diversity of deposited material are explained by the presence of a warm and humid climate, with a significant amount of water carrying suspended material (STEJIC, 1997).

Due to the low slope along the longitudinal river profile, the large width of the alluvial plain, and the presence of all facies of river accumulation during the Quaternary, it can be said that the Sava River valley was in a constructive dynamic phase. South of the Sava River, during the prevailing uplift and erosion of Neogene deposits, rivers such as Tamnava, Kolubara, Vukodraž, Vukićevica, etc., deposited mainly fine-grained sediments of terraced floodplains, of a monocyclic type, where the flow strength abruptly decreases. According to STEJIC (1997) this resulted in the formation of Pleistocene terraces at relative heights of 80-110 m and 40-60 m,

represented by channel and floodplain facies. This type of sedimentation corresponds to a perstrative dynamic phase (STEJČIĆ, 1997).

According to (STEJČIĆ, 1997) during the Middle Pleistocene, terrace deposits at a relative height of 25-35 m were formed both in the Sava River valley and in the valleys of its right tributaries. These sediments resemble true river terraces, but differences arise in particle size and qualitative composition. Due to the evident cooling and aridity of the climate, even in the Sava River valley, the sediments exhibit a monocyclic character.

Similar tectonic-climatic conditions persisted during the Late Pleistocene, leading to the formation of the 7-12 m relative height terrace. However, beyond the terraces at 40-60 m and 80-110 m relative height, the development of deluvial-eolian cover begins, indicating a cold and relatively wet climate (STEJČIĆ, 1997). Winds carrying dust from the north into the Pannonian Plain created loess deposits on the southern slopes of Fruška Gora. However, in the Lower Kolubara and Kolubarska Posavina, which is south from the European periglacial zone, wind strength was weakened, resulting in less eolian material, which was later or simultaneously re-deposited with sediments on the floodplain (GAUDENYI et al., 2022). These sediments, with a loess-like silt appearance, are intersected by duplicated buried soil, manifested in the form of decimeter layers with frequent inclusions. All these characteristics related to typical loess phenomena, as well as the very similar mineral composition of cover sediments and the floodplain, support the mentioned conclusion about the genesis of these sediments.

Within Holocene sediments, represented by numerous facies, the alluvial plain of the Sava River and much smaller alluvial plains and fans of its tributaries developed, with eolian sediments of the sandy covers of small diameters occasionally deposited during the late Holocene. The formation of the polygenic cover continued with a predominant contribution of deluvial processes. The results of field survey confirm that the alluvial sediments of the Sava were presented by occasionally flooded terraces at 3-5 m relative height and older Holocene floodplain sediments, while in the upper Holocene, alluvial deposits of channel, floodplain, alluvial fans and terrace facies were created. In the valleys of the right tributaries of the Sava, floodplain sediments with several layers of pseudo-buried soils and deposits of organic origin were developed. Throughout the Holocene, forms of floodplain cones were created by the action of intermittent flows, with the most prominent being the Vukodraž floodplain cone.

The current trend of erosion-accumulation processes remains similar today, with the additional anthropogenic impact (of human activities on nature), usually in a negative context. An illustration of such a poor environmental transition is the deposition of waste material from the Obrenovac thermal power plant along the banks of the Sava River. The human activities shown as legal and illegal gravel- and sand pits in on the remnants of alluvial fan it caused faster erosion. The intensive agriculture also made the uppermost surface more mobile. The bed sediments of streams in the vicinity of Obrenovac thermal power plant moved and transformed into the canals. The regulation of Kolubara River and unsuitable management for cleaning its valley caused sometimes additional floods on some segments of its catchment.

Fig 2. Geological map of Lower Kolubara and Kolubarska Posavina based on this study. Based on studies of Stejić (1997) and Filipović et al. (1980) (The map used international symbols, explanation in Serbian).

Terraces on the left bank of Kolubara River

The results shown that the relief of Kolubara valley is affected often with torrential floods and it has a significant impact on land surface dynamics which is manifested mainly as bank erosion (Dragičević et al., 2007, 2012, 2013, 2017; Kostadinov et al., 2017; Roksandić et al., 2011). The left tributaries of Kolubara River should have torrential flood fluvial architecture, and it enables to form a set of alluvial fans on the contact with the Kolubara alluvial plain. Basically the facies which previously described as terraces of the Kolubara River they are alluvial fans of its tributaries. The alluvial fans' sediments contain unsorted, coarser material lack of fossil record.

The relief characteristics shown that along the left Kolubara valley suitable conditions formed for the alluvial fan forming processes. Their genesis starts when the meandering Kolubara River (and Tamnava River) eroded its left banks. It resulted to forming hanging valley of the left tributaries of Kolubara- and Tamnava River. The torrential floods at the place where eroded the left bank of Kolubara and Tamnava started an alluvial fan forming process along its left valley, from the material deposited by the left tributaries of Tamnava- and Kolubara River (STEJČIĆ, 1997) (Fig. 2).

Remnants of (macro) alluvial fan of Obrenovac

Based on the geological map of FILIPOVIĆ et al., (1970) it is clear that in Kolubarska Posavina the sediments of the Kolubara River could contain gravels while the Sava River sediments are exclusively composed of finer grain size sediments (sand-silt-clay). According to the results of investigations the former macro alluvial fan formed in the mouth of Kolubara to Kolubarska Posavina (marked as *am* and *ap* in Fig. 2). It ascends from the line Zvečka – Mislođin and northwards to it on the alluvial plain of the Sava River. We used the term macro alluvial fan because its diametry shows larger dimensions than the other alluvial fans in the Kolubara valley southwards of Kolubarska Posavina. It seems very likely that on the remnants of alluvial fan formed the town of Obrenovac. A few gravel pits in the vicinity of Obrenovac confirm it, however the gravel can be exclusively associated with the Kolubara river sediments (they cannot be associated with the sediments of the Sava River in Kolubarska Posavina which are silt-mud predominant sedimentary environment characterizes, the gravels likely to be linked with the strong energy streams which can be easily linked of torrents). Moreover, the fluvial erosion Kolubara River moving the majority of alluvial fan sediments northwards to the Sava River so only in fragments were preserved this big alluvial fan (the northernmost fan which is marked as *pr* in Fig. 2). The active nealpine tectonics and the tectonics control was essential of its formation (e.g. MAROVIĆ et al, 2007, WHIPPLE & TRAYLER, 1996) had also an impact on the erosion in the Kolubarska Posavina for the mentioned alluvial fan.

Recent position of the Kolubara River

The recent position of Kolubara in the Kolubarska Posavina moved eastwards (Fig. 2). The general explanation is related to the of Baer's Law of Stream Deflection

(e.g. GOUDIE, 2004), neotectonics and meandering pathways (DIMITRIJEVIĆ & DIMITRIJEVIĆ, 1989). It seems evident that the large quantities of sediment also have impacts on that change its course to not only the Baer's Law of Stream Deflection which implies to be move eastwards also.

Sedimentary provenance of Kolubarska Posavina

The fluvial deposition systems should and the sedimentary record are the keys to identify the sedimentary provenances (MIALL, 1996). According to the research results the based on the grain size composition and the paleomeanders reconstruction after a landform characteristics, the sediment samples eastwards from the Zvečka (the older meander) which shows differences in coarser grain size composition than those in the Zvečka meander. These results were supported with the results of geological mapping (FILIPOVIĆ & RODIN, 1980). The sedimentary provenance shows the older (Zvečka) meander of the Sava River should be its easternmost part, while east from it should be the sediment cover of the Kolubara River (BOŽOVIĆ et al, 2024). The Sava River sediments mainly contain its grain size ratio in between sand and clay, its angularity classification of coarse-grained sediment particles defined as subrounded or rounded. The Kolubara River sediments we can find also pebbles and gravels. The angularity classification of coarse-grained sediment particles shape varies from rounded, subrounded, subangular and angular. Nearby Obrenovac the gravels found in exposures imply that the sediments provenance linked to the Kolubara River sediments.

DISCUSSION

The right bank erosion phenomena

The moving of rivers westwards from its course the scientist linked with the Baer's Law (GOUDIE, 2004) and Coriolis force (BALLA, 2009a; 2009b). GOUDIE (2004) briefly explains that Baer's Law (also could find under: Baer's - Babinet Law or Baer - Slosov's Law) proposes a mechanism by which the Earth's rotation affects the formation of river pathways. The hypothesis suggests that due to the Earth's rotation, erosion predominantly takes place on the right banks of rivers in the Northern Hemisphere and on the left banks in the Southern Hemisphere.

BALLA (2009a; 2009b) in his studies suggest that the Coriolis force manifests when moving towards or away from the center of rotation. This phenomenon occurs in a rotating frame of reference, such as a five-meter-wide rotating disk on a playground. For instance, when positioned halfway between the center and the rim, your rotational speed is half that of the speed at the rim, reaching zero at the center. Stepping towards the rim without the requisite rotational speed creates a perceived sideways acceleration against the rotation direction. As you gradually move towards the rim, the apparent sideways acceleration diminishes due to the extended time it takes for the rotational speed deficit to accumulate. Consequently, the magnitude of the Coriolis force is directly proportional to the radial component of your speed relative to the center of rotation, with its direction perpendicular to the path towards the center of rotation.

However, this situation is different than the Baer's Law and Coriolis force defined in the case of Drina River. The Drina River moved westwards, due to the great amount of transported gravels, on its alluvial fan to reach its recent bed.

Moreover, we can conclude that not only a sole factor made on river course moving impacts. It is necessarily to analyze all potential factors related the river course changes. It seems more likely that in case of Kolubara River the Coriolis Effect does impact the meandering of rivers, however it is not always a rule.

The vertical deflection can be referred to as a Coriolis Effect and is a maximum at the Equator. This effect, stemming from the Earth's rotation, causes a deflection to the right in the Northern Hemisphere and to the left in the Southern Hemisphere for moving objects. This deflection influences the flow of rivers, contributing to the development of their meandering patterns as they follow the route of least resistance. Despite the Coriolis effect playing a role, it's essential to acknowledge that other factors, including river discharge, sediment load, and underneath the surface geology, also contribute significantly to the formation of river meanders.

Several regional investigations as in the case of the Tisza river (e.g. GÁBRIS, 2001; GÁBRIS & NÁDOR, 2007; TIMÁR et al., 2005; UNGER & NÉMETH, 2013) shown the complexity of impact by many factors which resulted the riverbed migrations.

Fluvial terraces Vs alluvial fan

The geological maps (FILIPOVIĆ et al., 1980; STEJIĆ, 1997) served for basic information; however the primary goal of those maps was to identify the geologic record on chronostratigraphic principles. These maps serve the basic information the questioned sediment are Quaternary fluvial sediments, however the genesis was not in the focus of detailed investigations. The investigations of genesis of these fluvial sediments in the context of landform dynamics are important in our case because the alluvial fans suggest more instability conditions of the relief than terraces. In the excellent study of LARSON et al. (2015) described the genesis of the lateral erosion of the alluvial fans in the same drainage basin nearby the fluvial terraces, the remnants of the alluvial fans denominated as "toe-cutting" terrace. The confusion in terminology and morphological similarities among terrace forms have, in the past, led to misinterpretations, with toe-cut terraces being mistakenly identified as traditional fluvial terraces. To address this issue LARSON et al., (2015) suggest that future research adopts the term "toe-cut terrace" for clarity and precision in describing these landforms. The investigations and discussions with colleagues concluded that the proposed "toe-cut terrace" is not adequate because it implies to the terrace (it cannot be terrace due its genesis), it is simply an alluvial fan (in our case the Kolubara River tributaries). We will still keeping the term alluvial fan or remnants of the alluvial fan in the mentioned cases, not the so called "toe-cut terrace". Simply it is not a terrace, it is an alluvial fan, and in some cases if it is eroded we use the term remnant or segment of the alluvial fan.

CONCLUSIONS

The study aimed to make a revision on recent research on geological and geomorphological mapping in the Lower Kolubara and Kolubarska Posavina area. The

findings indicate that the left bank of the Kolubara valley, starting from the confluence of the Tamnava River, is primarily composed of alluvial fans from the Kolubara River's tributaries. Earlier investigations had identified these as Kolubara terraces.

The sedimentary provenance of Kolubarska Posavina can be divided into two main segments. The western segment, consisting mainly of former meanders and alluvial plains, terminates eastwards with the older - Zvečka (paleo)meander of the Sava River, belonging to the Sava River sedimentary system. The eastern segment, formed from the remnants of the (macro)alluvial fan of the Kolubara floodplain sediments, encompasses the area eastwards from the older (paleo)meander of the Sava river, considered the sedimentary area of the Kolubara River.

The importance of this study is to have better data of the superficial deposits and landform dynamics, which should give more exact data for the relief resistance to the increased vulnerability of landslides and erosion. In this study we identified that the left bank of Kolubara River have different properties as an erosion surface.

The sedimentary domains are very useful when some the groundwater sources are affected with pollution to know which area should be suitable for finding a groundwater source of better quality. In the case of Posavska Kolubara we can distinguish two sedimentary domains which would be very useful if some problems with the groundwater are identified. In one of the sedimentary domains if there will be some problems with water quality, with the new wells from the other sedimentary domains could solve the problem.

Limitations of our study are that for urban planning it would be used to evaluate this study in higher resolution with more detailed investigations.

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REZIME

Studija je imala za cilj da uradi evaulaciju novijih istraživanja u vezi sa geološkim i geomorfološkim kartiranjem područja Donje Kolubare i Kolubarske Posavine.

Istraživanja su se bazirala na postojećim podacima geoloških karta, satelitskih snimaka i urađena su terenska istraživanja prilikom kojih su se analizirali sedimenti Donje Kolubare.

Rezultati terenskih istraživanja ukazuju da je uz levu obalu doline Kolubare, od ušća reke Tamnave do Save formiran je plavinski zastor. Na ovoj deonici doline (Ušće Tamnave – Kolubarska Posavina), Kolubara je podsecala levu obalu. To se odrazilo da se na mestima pritoka najpre formirale viseće doline iz kojih su se kasnije formirale plavinske lepeze. Nakon veće količine deponovanog materijala plavinske lepeze su se spojile u vidu plavinskih zastora (označeno sa *pr* na Fig. 2). Ranija istraživanja su plavinski zastor identifikovala kao terase Kolubare.

Na prostoru Kolubarske Posavine na osnovu prinosa materijala sedimenti se mogu podeliti na dve glavne provincije. Zapadni segment Kolubarske Posavine, koji je uglavnom sastavljen od bivših meandara Save i sedimenata aluvijalne ravni, završava prema istoku sa starim (paleomeandom) meandrom reke Save (kod Zvečke), i pripada sedimentacionom sistemu reke Save. Istočni segment, koji je nastao od bivših ostataka (makro)plavine i sedimenata inundacione ravni Kolubare, obuhvata područje istočno od starog (paleomeandra) reke Save i smatra se sedimentacionim područjem reke Kolubare koja se tokom vremena promerala se istočnije.